

Assessment of Tourist Satisfaction Index of Trimbakeshwar Tourist Center in Nashik District, (Maharashtra)

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Abstract:

The current study aims to assess the tourist satisfaction index. The biggest and most well-known economic sector is the tourist sector. In many regions of the world, this well-liked industry is expanding quickly, creating opportunities for further expansion. This article seeks to determine the factors that affect visitors' satisfaction and loyalty to devotees and other tourists at the current holy site. Thousands of people travel from all over India to witness this historically significant and spiritual site. Field work was organized to collect visitor views, attitudes, and recommendations recorded in well-designed questionnaires, group discussions, and surrounding personal observations during the field survey. The purpose of this work was to evaluate visitor satisfaction and identify current facilities and their level of development. During the field study, 296 questionnaires were completed by tourists. The visitor satisfaction ratings of a subset of facilities were calculated using the converted arithmetical replies. Four categories-excellent, good, satisfactory, and unsatisfactory were created based on the evaluation of visitor satisfaction. The overall satisfaction level at this place is satisfactory, with an average score of 26.24 percent. Planning and development of this religious tourism destination in the future may benefit from using the average of the Trimbakeshwar holy site satisfaction index.

Key words: tourist satisfaction index, excellent, good, satisfactory, unsatisfactory.

Introduction:

The history of human travel is the starting point for the history of tourism. walking while looking for food or a place to be safe from the elements. The study of travel and tourism history aids in our comprehension of how historical development shaped tourism in the present. The goal of tourism nowadays is to make visitors happy, healthy, and hearty (Sunetra Roday 2013). Today's fast speeds, motors, ships, and airplanes have all changed the tourism industry as a whole. These days, more people are traveling to tourist locations every day. Every region has an abundance of tourist attractions to draw visitors. Every tourism destination has a variety of visitor kinds.

As a result, research on the functional and behavioural elements of tourists is crucial for both the growth of the travel industry and center planning. the examination of visitor profiles with respect to gender, age, marital status, country of origin, profession, education, reason for visit, income, duration of stay, mode of transportation, frequency of visit, information source about tourism hub, and perceptions of amenities at tourist destinations. shows the norm for visitors and the traits that make them behave that way. The growth and advancement of centres can benefit from all of this information on visitors and their opinions about tourism destinations. In the evaluation of the tourist and tourism centre's behavioural and functional features at the Trimbakeshwar tourism centre. To

gather primary data for the study region, a survey was undertaken.

Religious centres make up the Trimbakeshwar tourism centre. A test survey was carried out using pre-made questionnaires. The tourists were chosen at random to participate in interviews and complete the questionnaires. The locations of Trimbakeshwar Temple, Swami Samarth Ashram, and Dugarwadi, Waterfall were chosen for the sample survey. At a chosen visitor centre in the study location, nearly 296 travellers were personally contacted and asked to complete questionnaires.

Study Area:

Trimbakeshwar tourism centre is located on the Western side of Nashik city. it is situated in Trambak Tahsil of Nashik district. Trimbakeshwar is situated partly in the Dhamanganga basin and partly in the Godavari and Vaitarna Basin. It lies between 19⁰ 55' and 19⁰ 56' North latitude and 73⁰ 31' and 73⁰ 32' east longitude. Trimbakeshwar tahsil has an area of 898.38 sq. km and a population of 168423 as per the 2011 census. There are 122 villages in this Tahsil. The tahsil has three Rivers namely Godavari Dhamanganga and Vaitarna. The Tahsil is surrounded by the Thane district in the west, and Peth tahsil in the North. Nashik tahsil in eastern and Igatpuri tahsil in the south of Trimbakeshwar.

Objectives of the Study:

- i. To study the satisfaction levels of available facilities at Trimbakeshwar tourist place.

Data Sources and Methodology

“Nowadays tourism is one of the important activities. It’s also called the tourism industry. So, tourist satisfaction is the most important factor for tourism growth. In India, satisfied tourist is the best and very powerful publicity medium on the other side dissatisfied tourists would be injurious to the

Formula:

$$Sti = \frac{\epsilon Mi Ni}{N}$$

Where,

Sti = Satisfaction Index for the ‘ith Factor

Mi = Numerical value for a particular level of Satisfaction for the ‘ith Factor.

Ni = Number of the respondent deriving a particular level of Satisfaction for the ‘ith Factor.

N = Total Number of Respondents for that factor for all levels of Satisfaction.

In this research, an attempt has been made to measure the satisfaction of tourism, facilities and services available in Trimbakeshwar center in Nashik district of Maharashtra.

The present research was done by using a random sample survey method. Primary data is collected during the fieldwork with the help of questionnaires. The Opening of the tourist nine facilities and services is a consideration, such as darshan, accommodation, transportation, and drinking water, personal safety, about destination, food and local citizenry.

The researcher requested to tourists note their satisfaction with both the tourist centers. The tourist was asked to indicate their level of satisfaction concerning every factor Marks by Excellent, Good, Satisfactory and Unsatisfactory. Then these qualitative grades are converted into the quantitative term. The researcher has studied the 296 tourists in both the tourist Centers.

They were told to be given a point or mark out of 10 for a particular level of satisfaction. Tourists have given Preference as Good,

industry. It has become increasing importance for destination management.”

“The level of satisfaction of any person is a state of mind. Many types related to satisfaction were measured by various scholars such as Employee Satisfaction, Job Satisfaction, Customer Satisfaction and also tourist satisfaction. Josef (2000) The present research work is completed by research to measure the tourist satisfaction index who visited Trimbakeshwar tourist center.”

Satisfactory, Excellent and Unsatisfactory. The researcher has considered numerical values such as (8,9,10) for Excellent, (8,7,6) for Good, (6,5,4) for Satisfactory and (3,2,1) for Unsatisfactory. The average values for the different levels of satisfaction for different factors are calculated by of Calculation of Mean /Average in the table.

These values were multiplied by the respective frequencies, which is given the total satisfaction. The sum was divided by the total frequency for the respective factor, which gives the satisfaction index for that factor. The satisfaction formula was used to measure the tourist satisfaction index.

Analysis of Satisfaction Index:

The data about the Opinion of tourists regarding the facilities available at the Trimbakeshwar tourist center, were collected through the questionnaire. The factor wise level of satisfaction is shown in table No. 1. Factor wise level of satisfaction (M I) (Number of tourists as per facilities available for the ‘Ith factor.)

Table 1: Factor wise Level of Satisfaction (Mi)

Sr. No.	Management Factor	Excellent		Good		Satisfactory		Unsatisfactory		Total	Total
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1	Accommodation	127	42.91	74	25.00	52	17.57	43	14.53	296	100
2	Transportation	143	48.31	82	27.70	65	21.96	6	2.03	296	100
3	Food	102	34.46	86	29.05	65	21.96	43	14.53	296	100
4	Darshan	106	35.81	73	24.66	82	27.70	35	11.82	296	100
5	Drinking Water	127	42.91	78	26.35	52	17.57	39	13.18	296	100
6	Health	138	46.62	52	17.57	60	20.27	46	15.54	296	100
7	Local People	129	43.58	84	28.38	49	16.55	34	11.49	296	100
8	About Destination	149	50.34	91	30.74	32	10.81	24	8.11	296	100
9	Safety	168	56.76	79	26.69	30	10.14	19	6.42	296	100
Total		1189	401.69	699	236.15	487	164.53	289	97.64	2664	900
Percentage		44.63		26.24		18.28		10.85			100.00

Source: Compiled by Researcher

The analysis is presented in the above table. It is concerned with the views of 296 tourists who

were interviewed at Trimbakeshwar (Dugarwadi Waterfall, Swami Samarth Ashram and

Trimbakeshwar Temple) on different affairs. There are nine factors that will influence the industry. The tourist views about the overall facilities at Trimbakeshwar are considered while counting on the satisfaction index. As per the opinion of 44.63% tourists, reported that all the installations are

excellent at Trimbakeshwar. The bulk of the tourists noted that all the installations are good i.e. 26.24%. 18.28% tourists are satisfied with all facilities at the finish. Just 10.85% tourists who are not satisfied with the facilities provided to them at the tourist spot.

Table 2: Factor Wise Average of Satisfaction (Ni)

Sr. No.	Management Factor	Average Satisfaction Index (%)			
		Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory
1	Accommodation	8.12	6.42	4.06	1.57
2	Transportation	7.50	6.09	4.55	1.07
3	Food	8.02	6.39	4.00	1.41
4	Darshan	8.04	6.03	3.01	1.22
5	Drinking Water	8.02	6.37	3.83	1.20
6	Health	7.64	6.22	3.88	1.11
7	Local People	7.86	6.08	3.86	1.20
8	About Destination	8.12	6.56	4.40	1.86
9	Safety	8.97	6.60	3.76	1.33

Source: Compiled by Researcher

Table 3: Factor wise Percentage Satisfaction Index

Sr. No.	Management Factor	Percentage Satisfaction Index			
		Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory
1	Accommodation	8.10	6.40	4.06	1.57
2	Transportation	7.50	6.09	4.24	1.23
3	Food	7.00	6.34	4.01	1.40
4	Darshan	7.00	6.02	4.23	1.02
5	Drinking Water	8.08	6.37	3.84	1.00
6	Health	7.60	6.46	3.73	1.11
7	Local People	7.91	6.03	3.94	1.16
8	About Destination	8.10	6.56	4.35	1.93
9	Safety	7.90	6.56	3.63	1.33

Source: Compiled by Researcher

Factor wise average satisfaction index and percentage satisfaction index are calculated. For this function, the tourists were required to assign points (0 to 10) for the exceptional stage of satisfaction

they derived from each component. The values for the different point of satisfaction for different components are presented in table 2 & table 3.

Table 4: Factor wise Satisfaction Index with Rank (Sli)

A. Percentage Satisfaction Index Method				B. Average Satisfaction Index Method			
Sr. No	Management Factor	Satisfaction Index	Rank	Sr. No	Management Factor	Satisfaction Index	Rank
1	Accommodation	6.03	1	1	Accommodation	6.04	1
2	Transportation	5.76	5	2	Transportation	5.76	5
3	Food	5.93	3	3	Food	5.95	3
4	Darshan	5.46	9	4	Darshan	5.43	9
5	Drinking Water	5.57	7	5	Drinking Water	5.60	7
6	Health	5.72	6	6	Health	5.72	6
7	Local People	5.51	8	7	Local People	5.50	8
8	About Destination	5.99	2	8	About Destination	5.99	2
9	Safety	5.85	4	9	Safety	5.91	4

Source: Compiled by Researcher

The percentage satisfaction index and the average satisfaction index methods are compared in table no.4. It is noted that satisfaction index for accommodation facility is 6.04; for transportation facility 5.76; for food 5.95; for Darshan facility and

5.43 and for drinking water 5.60. The satisfaction index for health, local people, about the destination and personal safety of tourists are 5.72, 5.50, 5.99 and 5.91 respectively.

Agreeing to the survey, tourist's opinion regarding the accommodation facility gets 1st ranked. The destination gets 2nd rank, food facility got 3rd rank. The safety, transportation, health, drinking water and local people get 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th and 9th rank respectively.

The satisfaction index for the accommodation, tourist destination and food facility got high ranks. These elements are more important for the tourism development at Trimbakeshwar. The accommodation facilities are significant in the survey region. Tourist sites are attractive in Trimbakeshwar. The actual aim of tourists is to get relaxation of mind. Darshan facility receives a 9th rank. Darshan, drinking water, attitude of local people facilities must be amended. For the fairs and festivals about 9 lakhs of tourists see this post and create problems of Darshan, food and accommodation. Local people may be given special facilities from their regular work, so that they will serve the tourists. Besides this, there safety, wellness and drinking water and other important facilities must be improved at Trimbakeshwar.

Conclusion:

The profile analysis of tourist views and behavioural attitudes about tourist centre. It is observed from the data analysis maximum number of tourists (79 %) came from within the Maharashtra state (21 %) of tourists came from other states of India. It is observed that the majority of the local tourist prefer to visit these tourist centres during festivals, Cultural Programme and at the time of Annual Fairs. It is recorded in Nashik district (29.27%).

It is observed that the majority of the tourists (84 %) are male and (16 %) tourists are female. It is found that 88.26 % of tourists' purposes are worshipped or doing religious activity. In Trimbakeshwar most of the tourists are came from all the states of India for various kinds of Rituals \ Pooja such as Narayannagbali, Pitrudosh, Tripindi pooja, Kalsarp, Rahu Ketu pooja etc.

It is observed that 42.24% of tourists used S.T. bus (M.S.R.T.C) services as their mode of transportation and followed by owned vehicles and also private vehicles. It is observed that about 62 % of tourists prefer one day stay followed by 2-3 days stay at a tourist centre.

It is observed that about 62 % of tourists not used the Accommodation facility at the tourist centre followed by Lodge & Hotel (19.45%). It is found that Pune, Mumbai and Nashik districts are well connected by state and national highways both these district's maximum tourist centres are connected by District roads.

The ranking of the satisfaction index at Trimbakeshwar has been high for the majority of the factors such as the Accommodation facility, the safety of tourists, the behaviour of local people, accommodation facilities, cleanliness etc. The

lowest rank of facilities and services like a Darshan, public toilets, medical facilities, road condition, parking and guide facilities.

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